

PASSIVITY OF MAGNESIUM

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Magnesium exhibits passivity when exposed to atmosphere in the presence of ultra-violet radiations. The extent of passivity is measured by the displacement of copper from a solution of copper sulphate. A slow current of dry air does not passivate the metal, but a rapid current activates it in the dark and passivates it on irradiation. Ionised air, produced by vigorous bubbling through concentrated sulphuric acid and passed over P_2O_5 , passivates the metal, while pure dry hydrogen, similarly ionised, activates the metal under the influence of ultraviolet radiations.

Air from a gas holder was dried by passing through a wash bottle containing concentrated sulphuric acid and then through calcium chloride towers. The dried air was passed through a silica test tube and then through an ordinary test tube which was well wrapped with a piece of black paper. The source of ultraviolet rays was an iron arc provided with a clock-work mechanism for feeding the electrodes operating at a pressure of 100 volts. A silica trough through which cold water was kept constantly circulating was placed between the arc and the silica test tube to cut off the heat of the arc.

About 25 cm. length of magnesium ribbon was well polished with fine emery paper and then well cleaned with a filter paper. Two equal lengths of 10 cm. each were cut from the ribbon, folded into loops and were inserted into the silica and glass test tubes. The silica test tube was exposed to the ultraviolet light for 30 minutes. The ribbons were then dropped into two separate conical flasks each containing 25 c.c. of copper sulphate solution. The magnesium was allowed to remain in the solution for exactly 5 minutes (the reaction ceased after 3 minutes) after which it was removed by hooked glass rod and 10 c.c. of the solution were titrated with standard thiosulphate solution.

The following table gives readings at different rates of flow.

TABLE I

(In a blank experiment 10 c.c. of $CuSO_4$ soln. required 20.4 c.c. of thio soln.)

No.	Volume of air (in c.c./min.)	Thio needed for test tube exposed to light.	to dark.	Remarks
1	0	18 c.c.	18 c.c.	No effect
2	16.7	18	18	
3	23.3	18	18	
4	31.3	18	18	
5	100	18	18	
6	240	18	18	
7	600	18.2	17.9	Passivated in the light, slightly activated in dark.
8	700	18.35	17.9	Passivity increases.
9	900	18.50	17.9	Passivity further increases

The following conclusions are drawn from the above observations :

- (i) For moderate rates of flow of air there is no effect of irradiation.
- (ii) A rapid stream of air passivates the metal in light.
- (iii) A rapid stream of air slightly activates the metal.

Gases ionise when vigorously bubbled through concentrated sulphuric acid and certain electrolytes ; the ionisation is further increased by drying the gas over P_2O_5 . Air was bubbled through concentrated sulphuric acid at the rate of 100 c.c. per minute and was further passed over two drying towers containing P_2O_5 and was irradiated as in the previous experiment for 30 minutes. 18.6 C.c. of thiosulphate solution were required showing that the metal was highly passivated.

The effect of irradiation in a stream of pure, dry and ionised hydrogen was next tried. Hydrogen from a Kipp was bubbled through wash bottles containing lead acetate solution and silver nitrate solution and then through P_2O_5 towers. For moderate rate of flow, volume of thio was 17.1 c.c. and at 100 c.c. of gas per minute, the volume of thio was 16.8 c.c.

C O N C L U S I O N

A current of air rapidly bubbled through concentrated sulphuric acid and dried over calcium chloride has fewer chances of drying when compared with a slow stream of air, and the moisture, thus carried with the air under the influence of ultraviolet rays, produces an oxide film which makes the surface passive. The same rapid current of air in the dark sweeps off partly any film on the surface and slightly activates. Further, ionised air increases the passivity confirming the formation of an oxide film on the irradiated surface of the metal which becomes electro-positive. Similarly, the activation of the metal, when ionised hydrogen is passed over the electro-positive surface of the metal, proves the reduction of the oxide film. These experiments therefore support the oxide film theory of passivity.

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